

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)
Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication
ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060
Publisher: Binas Publishing
Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

RELI MARIA L. BARILLO, MBA
Instructor III
Negros Oriental State University
relimariabarillo@gmail.com

“MOTHER @ 94”

She is old, and I love her;
To me, she's the best mother.

Her mind is clear and speaks fast,
About her stories in the past.

How I wish to be like her,
At 94, she still thinks smarter.

I am so proud of her,
That's my mother.